

MEDIA DISRUPTIONS IN THE DIGITAL ERA: CONSEQUENCES FOR TOTAL NEWSPAPER MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: The internet came with disruptive tools that have helped much to articulate and integrate some of the mind burling innovations in media production and management. This has not been witnessed before. The disruptions have transformed life, media business and the global economy; making multimedia and online journalism and web newspaper publishing possible. This paper anchors on Schumpeter's (1942) creative destruction theory and Clayton Christensen's (1997) disruptive innovation theory. It adopts the qualitative conceptual study framework to examine the advent of the internet technology as a consequence of digitization and digital transformation and how it disrupted the traditional media production process including the printing technology and its newspaper press production process and ushers in a revolutionary trajectory in the mass media production and distribution system. The paper relied on secondary data sources to discuss concepts such as the newspaper press, the total newspaper concept, the changing media management landscape, timeline in technological disruptions in media communication, digitization, digitalization and digital transformation, multimedia and online journalism, media digital disruptions and the total newspaper concept. The paper argues that the internet made "media convergence" possible on the World Wide Web and provided other interactive accessories that creatively destroyed and innovatively disrupted the distinct, disparate and separate media production processes of the newspaper, radio and television and converge them on the World Wide Web as web or online newspaper.

Keywords: Media, Disruptions, Digital, Newspaper, Management

Introduction

Background

Twenty first century no doubt has witnessed dramatic and revolutionary transformations in the production and management processes of many sectors of the economy, including the media. The advent of the World Wide Web, hyperlink referencing, hypertext writing, search engines and social media applications of the internet made possible by the processes of media digitization, digitalization and digital transformation, has proved to be a major disruption in the traditional media production and management processes. Media digitalization ushered in an era of media and communication innovations that have provided disruptive techniques which have

transformed life, businesses and the global economy. This development has however also raised significant issues in multimedia and online newspaper publishing and management (Amobi & McAdams, 2014).

Digitalization of the media and its internet technologies came with disruptive innovations that offer endless possibilities in media economics and management. In newspaper publishing, more and more possibilities are still unfolding. For example, the traditional newspapers' print editions which were before now hindered by both geographic and demographic barriers can today plan their editorial productions in one location, print and distribute globally, courtesy of the internet and satellite printing technology. Internet applications have exerted a revolutionary impact on newspaper publishing and in fact on the industry's much admired and much acclaimed "total newspaper concept" (Willis, 1988). This is in terms of opening up multiple possibilities not only for newspaper contents production and for providing synergy among separate newspaper departments, but for the entire media communication process (information gathering, processing, storage, distribution, and feedback). The World Wide Web has made media convergence possible, lessens the burden of information distribution and opened up multiple media revenue streams.

Objective and Method of study

This study adopts the qualitative conceptual study framework. Qualitative based approach to data analysis has been accepted in the social science research circle, and operates from an "interpretative stand point". Qualitative studies do not search for the truth, but offer "truthful explanations to everyday living" (Odotola, 2014).

The study examines how the advent of media digitization, digitalization and the resultant internet applications have helped to disrupt otherwise moribund traditional media production process including the printing technology and its newspaper press production process and ushers in a revolutionary trajectory in the mass media production and distribution system. The internet disruptive technologies have helped much to articulate and integrate some of the mind boggling innovations in media production and management that has not been witnessed before. These methods have made multimedia and online journalism and web newspaper publishing possible.

Online or web journalism, including newspaper publishing on the web, according to Amobi & McAdams (2014) provides for real time multimedia convergence, which has helped to create synergy in media production process and offer possibilities for multiple revenue streams in media management. This development has revitalized and revolutionized newspaper publishing and management. In today's typical online newspaper for example, the news consumer's experience is enriched by multiple construction and presentation of a story in text, audio, video and even graphic animations. It is also not uncommon to find a 15 minute or 30 minute television commercial or a radio jingle and a podcast on a typical online newspaper, a feat nobody would have thought of before now.

However, to help achieve this general objective, this study discusses in specific terms such concepts as the newspaper press, the total newspaper concept, the changing media management landscape, timeline in technological disruptions in media communication, digitization, digitalization and digital transformation, multimedia and online journalism, media digital disruptions and the total newspaper concept.

Theoretical framework

Two theories of technological revolution will guide the discussion of our topic, namely: (1) The theory of Creative destruction, (2) The theory of Disruptive innovation. They have been considered appropriate for understanding the topic

The theory of Creative destruction

Joseph Schumpeter in 1942 propounded the theory of creative destruction to refer to the process of innovations and changes in technology which results in the creative destruction of the existing economic structures such as industries, firms and jobs. Schumpeter believes that for an entrepreneur to be successful in the capitalist system he must introduce good ideas to replace the old ones. He defines this process as any new policy that reduces the overall cost of production or increases demand for products. Commenting on the theory, Adler (2019) described Creative destruction in business as deliberate efforts to destroy the old approach and create a new one that can guarantee the continued survival of the business. As an illustration, Adler (2019) says that incremental improvement may continue to be valuable and helps a business to acquire considerable price niche in the market, but with the introduction of creative destructive “technologies” obsolete processes and products will be effectively replaced by a superior innovation. Relating the theory to this study the internet has actually introduced creative destructive tools into media production and management to make the traditional media production and management process seem obsolete. This leads us to the next theory.

The theory of Disruptive innovation

Clayton M. Christensen, a Harvard Business School professor, propounded Destructive innovation theory in 1997. The theory assumes that an introduction of a new technology in any business can disrupt the existing business plans and models. According to Clayton & Rayner (2011) and Jones (2010) an opportunity for a disruptive innovation to occur comes when customers’ needs are not being met by an existing technology or can be met in a better way by another technology. The theory according to Isiaka (2015) suggests that successful businesses fail or stop growing and developing when an unexpected innovation is introduced into it to threaten an existing technology. Clayton (1997) separates new technologies into two categories, namely: Sustaining technology and Disruptive technology. While a sustaining technology relies on incremental improvement to already existing/established technologies, a destructive technology displaces entirely an existing one and shakes up the industry or provides a ground breaking product that creates a completely new industry. Destructive innovations according to Nwabueze (2018) may lack refinement, often have performance problems because they are new, appeal to a limited audience and may not yet have a practical application (such was the case with the “electrical speech machine invented by Alexander Graham, which has today become the telephone). Relating this theory to the topic under consideration, the digital transformation of the media and its internet have provided destructively innovative accessories such as “media convergence” on the World Wide Web, the search engines, the hypertext writing, the hyperlinks, etc, that have shaken up the newspaper industry and created completely new media production and management process (online-multimedia journalism) and a new product (the Web newspaper).

The newspaper press

The Newspaper is a valuable asset of any nation. Its resilience according to McQuail (2010) is unequalled among the mass media. Amobi & Hussein (2013) has stated that the newspaper is an aspect of the mass media outside of television, radio, cinema and the internet. The authors say that along with other printed matters newspapers are referred to as the press, taken from its major technology, the printing press. The authors state further that the newspaper has evolved with social, political, and economic development of societies. It has evolved into partisan, elite, and popular newspapers, each playing various vital social, political and economic

roles for the society.

Furthermore, McQuail (2010) says that the press has always specialized in human interest stories, in dramatic and sensational styles of reporting and presentation. The author recognizes the “elite press”, normally considered independent from the state and from vested interests as a major institution of political and social life, especially as a self-appointed former of public opinion and voice of national interest. The “elite press” according to the author tended to show a highly developed sense of social and ethical responsibility' and has fostered the rise of journalistic profession dedicated to balanced, fair and objective reporting of issues and events. These features of the newspaper press according to Okoye (2007) accounts for why societies, especially democratic ones began to assign sacred roles to the newspaper, such as monitoring governance, and holding government accountable and responsible to the people through news reportage.

Newspapers exist as vital information source about local, national and international social, political and economic events and issues. This underscores the importance of newspapers in society. Consequently, those who manage newspaper institutions, like all other successful managers of businesses, are expected to do so in a responsible and enlightened manner if their business must succeed. Managers of newspapers understand also that in today's changing business environment success means much more than mere survival. They therefore strive to put out newspapers that excel.

Willis (1988) however, has it that the newspaper industry overall, is probably no better managed than any other industry. According to the author, many journalists are individualistic and skeptical. They also know that they are in business that has great social impact, as such they tend to see the newspaper just as a social institution, forgetting that the newspaper is also a profit oriented business in materialistic term. Nevertheless, the first goal of any business is survival. Otherwise its mission whatsoever it is will be a mirage. So there arises the need for the journalist to balance social service ethic of the newspaper business with its market ethic.

However, concerned with balancing the newspaper business ethics (market and service), Willis (1988) pointed out the problem that the entire media mix has changed to the point that many newspapers are endangered, even some have gone under, a situation that calls for the adoption of the “Total Newspaper Concept”.

The Total newspaper concept

Communication and cooperation among separate newspaper departments, in contrast with the classical pyramidal management structure, are the major features of the Total Newspaper Concept. According to Willis (1988) Total Newspaper Concept was developed by the International Marketing Association (INMA) and rests on the beliefs that for a newspaper to be effective and efficient, its various departments (news and editorial, advertising, circulation, administration, etc.) must communicate, cooperate and coordinate efforts at becoming a superior newspaper ready to meet the challenges of the changing market. In addition to meeting those challenges the newspaper must concern itself with and respond to the needs of readers, nonreaders, advertisers and non-advertisers. Citing the International Marketing Association (INMA) Willis (1988) says that “total newspaper concept” embodies a fully integrated newspaper production and management process that is devoid of the classical pyramidal management structure. The pyramidal management structure tends to harbor the tendency to create departments with “tunnel visions” about their missions and how to achieve them. This integrated newspaper concept in contrast provides for a newspaper management, production and marketing structure that bring synergy to the news, advertising and circulation departments. The newspaper concept also

provides for the changing needs of the environment, the needs of the news consumers and advertisers as well as consumer intimacy, immediacy, deep market penetration and targeted circulation.

Total Newspaper Concept according to Willis (1988) exhibits the importance of interfacing between various newspaper departments and between the newspaper and the four broad target groups in the market. The offices, for example, of the publisher, personnel, promotion, accounting, marketing and the mechanical department must interface with the three main newspaper departments (news-editorial, advertising and circulation). These departments in turn must coordinate work with each other and conduct two-way communication with the newspaper's four target groups outside the newspaper. It is equally important according to the author to let the entire newspaper staff understand that it is on the same mission to produce a quality newspaper that must dominate its geographic and demographic market. Hence building synergy, communication and cooperation in the production and management system of the newspaper are the chief features of the Total Newspaper Concept. The total newspaper concept has however in line with Clayton (1997) proved to be a sustaining innovation relying on incremental improvement (Adler, 2009) to already existing/established production and management processes of the printing technology and the newspaper press.

The changing media management landscape

Nonetheless, the newspaper press has today witnessed creatively destructive and innovatively disruptive technologies that have transformed its production and management system. Presently, newspapers and other media forms are on the World Wide Web. A pertinent question one may ponder on is why newspapers and broadcast channels are on the web? To borrow an explanation from the Canadian communication scholar, Marshal McLuhan (n.d), the newspaper and other media forms are on the web because of the dominant medium of this age- the internet. The dominant medium of any age according to McLuhan dominates the people of that age and each new medium of communication causes cultural transformation in family life, work place, schools, healthcare, friendships, religion, recreation and politics. Kovach & Rosentiel (2001) agreeing with McLuhan has observed that when Telegraph was introduced in the 1830s, it brought with it significant social, economic and technological changes. For example, in the 1880s there came a drop in paper prices and a wave of immigration as a result. The coming of radio in the 1920s led to a rise in gossip and celebrity culture; and in 1950, television marked the era of Cold War (the advent of participatory journalism). Today with the coming of the internet, media business is experiencing a revolution as never before. Innovative technologies are displacing entirely existing ones and are shaking up the media industry and providing ground breaking products that create a completely new industry.

Presently, news business is witnessing divergence in practices and production processes between the traditional and the new media. This divergence is according to Amobi & McAdams (2014) underscored by momentous transitions and instantaneous transmissions and updates of news taking place on the internet. The immediacy brought by the online media space allows for little or no time for gatekeeper deliberations in content creation as the internet has brought with it the social media, with their multiplicity of producers (senders) and consumers (receivers). This reality has made the traditional media's linear paradigm a non-issue. News and information today move at tremendous speed with the World Wide Web providing a space for global connections irrespective of time and geography. Amobi & McAdams (2014) says that with the creation of this global community whose connection is determined by interests, online media businesses are taking advantage of their

unique publishing medium and their ever increasing popularity to make global gains. The newspaper medium is not left out of this revolution.

Timeline of technological disruptions in communication media

Nwabueze (2018) posits that the communication timeline has an active history in terms of progress made over time in the communication media. Technological advances in communication are the evolutions or gradual developments in the communication media of information/data capture, data processing, storage, retrieval, dissemination and feedback. The author says that the overall aim has been to achieve the intended communication outcomes, including knowledge, attitude formation, modification and change that may influence opinion and behavior in a particular way.

However, Nwabueze (2018) distinguishes disruptive communication media to be technological revolutions rather than evolutions in media and communication development trajectory. This distinction is in line with Clayton's (1997) position that disruptions in any field (including the media) are scientific inventions or methods that displace or change the existing pattern of life, transform businesses and the global economy. Disruptive technologies in communication according to Nwabueze (2018) therefore, are the media innovations that have displaced the existing ones and transformed media life, media businesses and the global media economics by changing the processes and patterns of media production and management. The author posits that such technological disruptions in the communication media have helped produced global "killer media corporations" such as CNN, Aljazeera, etc. and have also helped local community media to be accessed from any part of the world. In other words disruptive technology in the communication media has provided for both "globalization" and "glocalization" of information.

Nonetheless, communication timeline has had resemblances of technological disruptions, showing how they emerged and transformed the communication process. But when we mention the term disruption in the media discourse what normally comes to mind is the computer domain: its tools and practices thereof. If we consider that Nwabueze (2018) has it that any technology that came up and changed or improved the practices of media production and management is considered disruptive, we should then not forget to consider, however, that there have been disruptive technologies in the communication media in the past from the Guttenberg's printing press to Mark Zuckerberg's Facebook.

Nwabueze (2018) outlines some factors that could be used to key into and evaluate disruptively advanced communication media technologies. These factors include: attempts by these technologies to expand the communication horizon (beyond face to face interactions), attempts to expand the information processing mechanism (fast and efficiency), attempts to expand information dissemination (tele or distance), attempts to expand information retrieval systems (search engines), and attempts to expand information storage systems (electronics database, books, libraries). As an illustration, disruption in terms of expanding information processing mechanism occurred when the personal computer (pc) displaced typewriter and forever changed the way we work and communicate. Again, the innovative windows operating systems' combination of affordability and user-friendly interfaces were instrumental in the development of the personal computing industry in the 1990s. Personal computer disrupted the television industry as well as a great number of other activities. The television live-streaming, microwave point to point transmission and the cable network system that we have today changed broadcasting and broadcast of religious worship forever. Today's uses of the social

media (Facebook, Whatsapp, Twitter, Instagram, etc) brought individuality into family life and effectively disrupted family bonding and interpersonal interactions. This development made McLuhan's "medium is the message" mantra to no longer count, as viewing Television programmes no longer holds family members together. Family members now spend more of their time chatting with friends and acquaintances and getting connected on the web.

Furthermore, patterns of news dissemination, advertising, public relations and entertainment have transformed forever. With the internet the traditional mass media linear paradigm is effectively disrupted. It is no longer just one to many, but many to one and many to many. Electronic mails (e-mail) system and mobile phone short message services (SMS) have transformed the way we communicate largely displacing letter writing and disrupting the postal and greeting cards industries. Cell phone disrupted the telephone industry and made it possible for people to communicate quickly and cheap from any part of the globe. Where is NITEL (the infamous Nigerian telecommunication giant)? Laptops replaced desktops and smart phones have replaced both cell phones and laptops. The list seems endless.

Disruptions are also common place today in the media domain: in the field of journalism, broadcasting, publishing, public relations and advertising. Thanks to media digitalization technology of the internet. Digital transformation overall has availed the communication media (newspaper, book, radio, television, public relations and advertising), with the disruptive methods that have been able to change media life and global media businesses.

The internet has helped the journalist and the media consumers to communicate online and real time. Online journalism is journalistic presentation on the web or internet with a provision of the possibility of convergence (multimedia presentations). Amobi & McAdams (2014) says that Convergence has transformed multimedia journalism from its earliest forms to a more advanced stage, from the so called print journalism "stand-ups" on camera to fully integrated multimedia newsrooms.

Digitization, Digitalization and Digital transformation

The technology of the internet is a consequence of digitization, digitalization and digital transformation. It is important to distinguish between these terms. It is equally important that we understand the "language of digitization" which according to Fusaro (2023) includes not only the concepts of digitization, digitalization and digital transformation, but also the technologies and developments that are associated with them.

Digitization according to Monton (2022) focuses on a process that converts physical objects into digital formats, and also on organizing analog information into units of data called bits. This process enables computers to process, store and transmit such information. Digitalization on the other hand develops processes and changes workflows to improve manual or analog systems, while digital transformation integrate digital technology to most, if not all business operations.

With digital transformation, digital technology is incorporated into all aspects of the business to improve efficiency in workflows and create value for the customer. An example of digital transformation in media production would be when reporters and editors working on a particular newspaper edition in say The Sun or Punch newspaper, by the aid of computers gather, write and transmit news stories via the internet to different satellite print shops located in remote zones of their coverage areas for publication and distribution. This transcends the traditional newspaper production and distribution process that confines newspapers to geographic

and demographic regions.

This reality of the phenomena of digitization, digitalization, and digital transformation with the resultant internet technologies has constituted a major disruption in media production and management processes in the present era. Today, newspaper publishers, for example enjoy the luxury of conceptualizing, planning, producing and profitably distributing their products all over the globe from one location. This has never been possible if not for the disruptions brought by the internet and satellite printing processes.

Kahn & Dennis (2023) describes the internet as the network of computer networks, a system of computer networks and telephone lines with worldwide interconnectivity. The internet according to the authors has revolutionized mass communication, mass media and commerce by allowing various computer networks around the world to communicate, providing the transmission modes of the World Wide Web, Search engines, Social networks, Hypertexts writing, and Hyperlink referencing. Fusaro (2023) and Monton (2022) indicate that these internet transmission accessories constitute the technologies and trends associated with digitization, digitalization and digital transformation. The introduction of these novel digital facilities in media production has helped to creatively destroy and disruptively transformed existing media business plans and models, including that of the newspaper. This assumption as Clayton & Rayner (2011) and Jones (2010) explained has become a reality in today's newspaper production that news production needs and news consumers' needs are being met in a better way by these media technologies.

Online and multimedia journalism

Rosales (2006) describes online journalism as digital story telling using various techniques of radio, television and newspaper in conjunction with the interactive and other unique advantages of the internet in the mix. Deuze (1999, *ibid.*) says that online journalism is the production of digital content including text, audio, video, and graphics, produced more or less exclusively for presentation on the World Wide Web as the graphic interface of the internet. The possibility provided by the production, presentation and distribution of digital media content on the World Wide Web offers the journalist the opportunity to combine many journalistic practices into a world of creative and accurate story telling in ways that were not possible before the advent of the internet. Journalism production and management in multimedia and online format is a consequence of digitization, digitalization and digital transformation of the media production processes. These processes have not only become creatively destructive, but innovatively disruptive in today's media production and management landscape. Both Schumpeter (1942) and Clayton (1997) assumptions cannot be less correct.

However, "online" journalistic production does not necessarily mean "multimedia". The deference can be seen in the "shovel ware" practices of some newspaper houses today which seem to be just repackaging and uploading their print contents to the Web. Multimedia production in its strictest and best form entails "media convergence". According to Amobi & McAdams (2014), multimedia convergence is understood as more or less reluctant collaboration and piecemeal integration of formally distinct media operations. This is particularly observable in print's and broadcast's journalism fusion with an online counterpart. Deuze (2004) again describes multimedia journalism as the construction of a story out of more than one medium. This construction includes (but not limited to) audio, video, photos, music, graphic animations, interactive and hypertextual elements which are then published on the World Wide Web. From the 1990s the media industry has had a structure of convergent multimedia news organizations, with media corporations all over the world opting for at

least one form of cross media cooperation between formally separated staffers, newsrooms and departments. Convergence has created a synergy in the production and management processes of otherwise previously distinct media forms. According to Amobi & Adams (2014) “multimedia convergence has transformed the journalist from a” lonely wolf” into a team player, enhancing at the same time the limits of decision making in the production of news”.

Media digital disruptions and the total newspaper concept

The changes the internet has brought to the newspaper industry’s preferred “Total newspaper Concept” management model have been both revolutionary and disruptive. We recall that the Total newspaper concept model seeks synergy among distinct newspaper departments for the purpose of producing a newspaper that will not only survive, succeed, but dominate its geographic and demographic market in the changing market environment. Total newspaper concept has communication and cooperation as its chief features. Exploring therefore, how the creative destructions and innovative disruptions of the digital transformations (of the internet) impacted on Total Newspaper Concept could prove very interesting. This is the crux of this section.

News-editorial and the internet

Newspapers today exist on the World Wide Web as online or web newspapers, either separately, or as online version of an existing printed periodical. Today in Nigeria for example established print tabloids like *The Punch*, *This Day*, *The Guardian* and many more have their online versions. Others like *The Premium Times*, *The Sahara reporters*, etc., publish entirely on the web without hard-copies.

Web newspaper as it exists today thrives on the principle of media convergence, a form of cross-media cooperation and synergy between formally separated staffers, newsrooms and departments. It combines multimedia such as texts, video, audio, graphics and interactivity which enhances user friendliness (participation and experience). According to Verweij (2009) converged newsrooms offer more opportunities for the public to be informed and involved in a story. It also offers the journalist more integrated tools to tell the story, bringing together the depth of newspaper coverage, the immediacy of television and the interactivity of the World Wide Web. Convergence is a major disruption that has brought this synergy even beyond what total newspaper concept seeks to achieve.

Publishing on the web has completely disrupted the printing and newspaper press, revolutionized newspaper production process, creating better opportunities and transforming the newspapers press. Newspapers today can compete with their broadcast media counterparts in presenting breaking news in timelier manner and with immediate feedback. The migration away from the classical traditional printing process is also helping to cut cost of production. Online newspaper publishing does not require newsprint for production.

The World Wide Web being the graphic interface of the internet, along with search engines, social networking sites, hypertext writing and hyperlink referencing constitutes some of the most disruptive tools of the internet as a form of digital transformation of our time. These tools have had a revolutionary impact on newspaper production and management. The advent of the internet changed news and editorial production forever. Traditional print tabloids such as *The Punch*, *The Guardian*, or *The Sun* may enjoy the web luxury of the hyperlink referencing. Hyperlink is one of the most striking features of the web and refers to points on an online newspaper page that a reader can click on to be moved to another point on either the same document, on the same newspaper website or at some other sites on the World Wide Web. According to Severin and Tankard

(2001) hyperlinks are a particular form of hypertext defined as a non-sequential writing by Ted Nelson who introduced it in 1965. With the hyperlink referencing web newspapers are overcoming noncooperation and lack of communication that hitherto existed among the distinct and discrete media forms and have them converge on the print newspaper medium.

Convergence made possible by the internet and the World Wide Web is offering a better synergy for the newspaper. It has not only created a convergence of the formally distinct and discrete media forms under one roof, but also offers opportunity for synergy (communication and cooperation) between formally distinct newspaper departments. To illustrate, a typical today's Web 2.0 online newspaper provides a platform for a combined efforts by the editorial and advertising units of the print media to construct digital news story packages, plan and produce advertising copies in various media formats that may include texts, audio, video, photos, photo slide and graphic animation. These enhance consumer satisfaction and experience. A digital story and a digital advertising copy produced in various media formats (text, still pictures, 15/30 minutes commercials in video and audio formats) for the newspaper could be circulated to audiences, not only on the newspaper web site but also linked up to the social media platforms, even forwarded to e-mails via hyperlinks.

The interactivity feature of the web on another hand enables readers, nonreaders, advertisers and non-advertisers to give not just a feedback, but a timely and immediate feedback. This is a major revolution in the traditional newspaper printing process which requires days and weeks to receive and attend to letters to the editor and other feedbacks. Convergence thus satisfies the communication and cooperation needs that were the concern of total newspaper concept, in a much better way.

The credibility and strong brand recognition of some well-established publications and their close relationship with advertisers leverage their chances of survival on the web. This is to the point that some established newspapers like the *Wall Street Journal*, *The New York Times* and the *Washington Post* are creating online pay walls and charging subscription fees. This has created a multiple revenue stream in addition to hard copy sales and advertising revenue.

With media convergence of the World Wide Web and other interactive accessories the internet has no doubt creatively destroyed and innovatively disrupted the distinct, disparate and separate media production processes of the newspaper, radio and television and converge them on the World Wide Web as web or online newspaper.

References

- Adler, D. (2019). Schumpeter's theory of creative destruction, Engineering and public policy. Retrieved on 10/9/2023 from cmu.edu/epp/irle/irl
- Amobi, I. T., McAdams, M. (2014). Issues and Techniques in Multimedia and Online Journalism. Lagos: Concept Publications Limited.
- Amobi, I. T., Hussein, S. (2013). Boko Haram, the media and national security. *Communication Review*, vol. 7, 2013. University of Lagos: Dept. of mass communication.
- Clayton, M.C., Raynor, M.E. (2011). The Clayton Christensen Innovation Collection, Harvard Business press, jul. 19
- Clayton, M.C. (1997). The Innovators Dilemma: when new technologies cause great firms to fail. Retrieved on 10/9/2023 from en.m.wikipedia.org/

- Deuze, M. (2004). What is multimedia journalism1? *Journalism studies*, Vol.5, Number 2, pp. 139-152
- Fusaro, F. (2023) Digitization, Digitalization and Digital Transformation explained. Retrieved on 23/9/2023 from www.morehandigital.info, ISSN2673-1764.
- Isiaka .Z.A. (2015). Examining survival strategies employed by Nigerian newspapers against loss of readership and revenues. *New media and mass communication*. www.iiste.org ISSN 2224-3275(Online) vol. 35, 2015
- Jones, M.K. ((2010). “Accurate as of the timestamp” newspaper journalism ethics in a time of economic and technological change, PhD Dissertation submitted to the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill.
- Kahn, R., Denis, M.A., (2023), Internet: computer network. Science &Tech, Britannica. Retrieved on 23/9/2023 from www.britannica.com/tech
- McLuhan, M. (n.d) BrainyQuote.com. Retrieved on 24/9/2023 from www.Brainyquote.com/quotes/quotes/m/marshalmc39979.html
- McQuail, D. (2010). McQuail’s Mass communication theory (6th. ed). London: Sage.
- Monton, A.L.,(2022). Digitization, Digitalization and Digital Transformation. Retrieved on 23/9/2023 from www.globalsign.com.
- Nwabueze, C. (2018). Technological Advances in communication. Unpublished lecture notes. Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam: Department of mass communication
- Odutola, K. (2014). When they came (for Olatunji Dare), in Adebani W.(2014) *Public Intellectuals, Public Sphere And Public Spirit* ,Ibadan: Ibadan University Press
- Okoye, I. (2007). Nigerian press laws and ethics. Lagos: Malthouse press ltd
- Rosales, R.G. (2006). The elements of online journalism. New York: iUniverse Inc
- Schumpeter, J. (1942). Creative destruction. Retrieved on 12/9/2023 from www.investopedia.com/terms/c/creativedestruction.asp
- Verweij, P. (2009). Making convergence work in the newsroom: A case study of print, radio, television and online newsrooms at the African media matrix in South Africa during the national arts festival. Vol. 15(1): DOI 10.1177/1354856508097020.
- Willis, J. (1988). Surviving in the Newspaper Business: Newspaper management in turbulent times. New York: Preager